

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha (UniProt ID: P50148) for use in western blot and flow cytometry

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Abstract

Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha (Gαq) is a heterotrimeric G-protein that mediates intracellular signalling downstream of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs). Somatic activating mutations in GNAQ cause constitutive, receptor-independent signalling and persistent activation of downstream pathways, promoting abnormal cellular proliferation, survival, and disease pathogenesis. Due to its central role in oncogenic and vascular disorders, Gαq is an important target for understanding disease mechanisms and developing therapeutic strategies. However, the performance and specificity of commercially available antibodies targeting Gαq have not been systematically evaluated.

In this study, we systematically evaluated eleven commercial antibodies for western blot and flow cytometry using a standardized knockout validation approach in human HAP1 cells, comparing readouts in GNAQ knockout lines with isogenic parental controls. These experiments form part of a larger collaborative initiative to address antibody reproducibility by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins and making the results openly available to the community. While antibody use and protocol conditions will vary between laboratories, this report provides a resource to guide selection of the most suitable reagents for studies of Gαq in health and disease.

Keywords

P50148, GNAQ, Gαq, Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha, antibody validation, western blot, flow cytometry.

Introduction

Aberrant activity of GNAQ, which encodes Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha (Gαq), has been implicated in several diseases, including uveal melanoma, and congenital vascular disorders (1, 2). Under physiological conditions, Gαq activates phospholipase C-β, leading to the generation of second messengers that regulate intracellular calcium release and protein kinase C activity, thereby influencing key cellular processes including proliferation, differentiation and survival (3). However, somatic activating mutations such as GNAQ^{Q209L} impair GTP hydrolysis, resulting in constitutive, receptor-independent signalling and persistent activation of downstream pathways including the MAP kinase cascade, thereby establishing GNAQ as a dominant-acting oncogene (4). As such, Gαq represents an important target for elucidating disease mechanisms and for the development of potential therapeutic strategies. Nevertheless, the reliability of commercially available antibodies targeting Gαq has not been systematically assessed, limiting reproducibility and interpretability of experimental results.

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterising commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols (5) and openly sharing the data (6). Here we evaluated the performance of eleven commercial antibodies for Gαq for use in western blot and flow cytometry, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Gαq properties and function. The platform for antibody characterisation used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterisation procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardised consensus antibody characterisation protocols are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterisation data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret the antibody characterisation data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (7).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT (wild type) and KO cells (8-10). The first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcript per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655). The cell line HAP1 expresses the *GNAQ* transcript at $4.3 \log_2$ (TPM+1). A *GNAQ* KO cell line was obtained from Horizon discovery (Table 1).

To screen all eleven Gαq antibodies by western blot, protein lysates from both HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cell lines were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed in parallel with eleven Gαq antibodies (Figure 1).

For flow cytometry, HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilised and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Eleven Gαq antibodies were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 2-4.

In conclusion, we screened eleven Gαq commercial antibodies by western blot and flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced using human HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells. High-quality and renewable antibodies capable of successfully detecting Gαq were identified.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Gαq antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these

partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Gαq, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Gαq experts are invited to analyse and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots. Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Methods

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

Antibodies

All Gαq antibodies are listed in Table 2, together with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRID), to ensure antibodies are cited properly (11). Secondary antibodies used in this study are provided in Table 3. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations.

Cell culture

All cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1, alongside their corresponding RRIDs, to ensure proper citation (12). Cells were cultured in IMDM (Thermo Fisher Scientific #31980030) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific #A5256801) and 1% antibiotic/antimycotic solution (Capricorn Scientific #AAS-B). All cell lines used in this study were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

For lysate preparation, HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells were washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #70011044) and lysed in RIPA buffer containing 1x of protease inhibitor cocktail, sodium orthovanadate and phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (Santa Cruz Biotechnology #sc-24948). Lysates were sonicated (40% amplitude for 5 seconds) three times and incubated for 30 minutes on ice prior to centrifugation at 20,000 x g for 1 hour at 4°C.

Protein concentration was confirmed using the Pierce BCA protein assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific #23225) and 30µg of protein was used. Samples were combined with Laemmli sample buffer (Bio-Rad #1610747) containing 2-mercaptoethanol (final concentration 355mM) (Sigma Aldrich #M7522) before being heated at 65°C for 10 minutes. Samples were then loaded in precast 4-20% WedgeWell Tris-Glycine Plus midi gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific #WTG42020BOX) alongside Prime-Step prestained broad range protein ladder (BioLegend #773302). SDS-PAGE was then performed in SureLock Tandem Midi Gel tanks (Thermo Fisher Scientific #STM1001) and run at 200V for 1 hour with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad #1610772). Proteins were then transferred to 0.2µm supported nitrocellulose membranes (Cytiva #10600015) using a Criterion blotter with plate electrodes (Bio-Rad #17004070) run at 85V for 45 minutes. Proteins on the blot were visualised with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific #161470250) which was scanned to show alongside individual western blots. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hour except for antibody 3992 which was blocked in 5% BSA in Tris-buffered saline containing 1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J77500.K2). Primary antibodies were then incubated overnight at 4°C in 5% milk TBST with gentle shaking. Following three ten-minute washes with TBST, horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated secondary antibodies were incubated at a dilution of 1/10000 (0.1µg/mL) in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hour at room temperature followed by three ten-minute washes with TBST. Membranes were then incubated with either Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific #32106) for 1 minute or Clarity Western ECL substrate (Bio-Rad #1705061) for 5 minutes prior to detection with the ImageQuant LAS 4000.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells were detached, and five million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were centrifuged at 300 x g, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). The two populations were combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Saponin (Sigma-Aldrich #558255) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% Saponin PBS with primary Gaq antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (Table 3) in 150 µl of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µl of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO

and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the GNAQ antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

Grant information

This work was supported by a grant from the National Centre for the Replacement, Refinement and Reduction of Animals in Research (NC3Rs) and MRC (NC3Rs Ref: NC/NAM0019/1, MRC UKRI076) alongside support from the Leicester Institute for Precision Health.

The funders have no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Miltenyi Biotec, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgments

This is a summary of independent research funded by both the NC3Rs and MRC and carried out at the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Leicester Biomedical Research Centre (BRC). The views expressed are those of the author(s) and not necessarily those of the NC3Rs, the MRC, the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

We gratefully acknowledge the support of Dr. Carl Laflamme and Dr. Riham Ayoubi, whose technical expertise were invaluable to this work

References

1. Trogdon M, Abbott K, Arang N. et al. Systems modeling of oncogenic G-protein and GPCR signaling reveals unexpected differences in downstream pathway activation. *npj Syst Biol Appl.* 2024 July 16.
2. Zecchin D, Knöpfel N, Gluck AK, Stevenson M, Sauvadet A, Polubothu S, et al. GNAQ/GNA11 Mosaicism Causes Aberrant Calcium Signaling Susceptible to Targeted Therapeutics. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology.* 2024 April; 144(4):811-819

3. Pilch J, Mizera J, Tota M, Donizy P. GNAQ/GNA11-Related Benign and Malignant Entities-A Common Histoembriologic Origin or a Tissue-Dependent Coincidence. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2024 Oct 30;16(21):3672
4. Van Raamsdonk CD, Bezrookove V, Green G, Bauer J, Gaugler L, O'Brien JM, et al. Frequent somatic mutations of GNAQ in uveal melanoma and blue nevi. *Nature*. 2008 Jan 29;457(7229):599.
5. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Bolivar SG, Alende C, Moleon VR, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nature Protocols*. 2024 Dec 17.
6. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *eLife*. 2023 Nov 5;12.
7. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made. *F1000Research*. 2023 Oct 16.
8. Biddle MS, Alende C, Fotouhi M, Jones C, Ayoubi R, Southern K, et al. A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Synaptotagmin-1 (Uniprot ID P21579) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and flow cytometry. *F1000Research*. 2024 Jul 19;13:817–7.
9. Cooper J, Jones C, Dixon K, Gooptu B, Virk H, Biddle M. A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for alpha-1-antitrypsin (uniprot ID: P01009) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation and flow cytometry. *F1000Research*. 2026 Jan 19;15:73.
10. Biddle M, Cooper J, Jones C, Dixon K, Virk H. A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for MMP7 (uniprot ID: P09237) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation. *F1000Research*. 2026 Jan 19;15:74.
11. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2023 Jan 6;51(D1):D358–67.
12. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *Journal of Biomolecular Techniques : JBT*. 2018 May 10;29(2):25–3

Table 1. Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalogue number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon	HZGHC004862c012	CVCL_SQ14	HAP1	GNAQ KO

Table 2. Summary of the Gαq antibodies tested.

Company	Catalogue number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Stock concentration (µg/mL)	Vendor recommended applications
Abcam	ab199533**	GR322678-4	AB_3668837	Recombinant Monoclonal	EPR17149	Rabbit	2199	WB
Abcam	ab210004**	GR3283939-6	AB_2934134	Recombinant Monoclonal	EPR20978	Rabbit	525	FC-Intra, IHC, IP, WB
Abclonal	A21111**	4100000075	AB_3668861	Recombinant Monoclonal	ARC3048	Rabbit	2000	ELISA, IHC, WB
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP54635_P050	QC23498-191019	AB_10578882	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	WB
Cell Signalling Technology	14373**	1	AB_2665457	Monoclonal	D5V1B	Rabbit	59	WB
Cell Signalling Technology	3992	1	AB_2111806	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	180	IHC, IP, WB
Novus Biologicals	NBP3-32395**	H681808001	AB_3282355	Recombinant Monoclonal	JE65-59	Rabbit	1000	IHC, WB
Proteintech	13927-1-AP	00053390	AB_2111647	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-49175*	ZJ4522111	AB_3074833	Monoclonal	13H4	Mouse	500	FC, IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-50816**	ZJ4520956D	AB_3094237	Recombinant Monoclonal	JE65-59	Rabbit	1000	IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-54020**	ZJ4520962	AB_3248491	Recombinant Monoclonal	23GB1295	Rabbit	1500	ICC/IF, WB

* Monoclonal antibody, ** Recombinant antibody.

ELISA = Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, FC = Flow cytometry, ICC/IF = Immunocytochemistry/ immunofluorescence, IHC = immunohistochemistry, IP = immunoprecipitation, WB = Western blot.

Table 3. Summary of the secondary antibodies used.

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalogue number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Application	Stock concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H + L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Mouse (H + L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625

Figure 1: Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(q) subunit alpha antibody screening by flow cytometry

Figure legends

Figure 1: Gαq antibody screening by western blot using protein lysates

Protein lysates from HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells were collected, and 30µg of protein was used for western blot with the indicated Gαq antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab199533** at 1/1000, ab210004** at 1/1000, A21111** at 1/1000, ARP54635_P050 at 1/1000, 14737** at 1/1000, 3992 at 1/1000, NBP3-32395** at 1/500, 13927-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-49175* at 1/1000, MA5-50816** at 1/1000 and MA5-54020** at 1/2000. Predicted band size: 42.1kDa. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Gαq antibody screening by flow cytometry (PFA-saponin)

HAP1 WT and *GNAQ* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% saponin. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated Gαq antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab199533** at 1/21990, ab210004** at 1/5250, A21111** at 1/2000, ARP54635_P050 at 1/500, 14737** at 1/590, 3992 at 1/180, NBP3-32395** at 1/1000, 13927-1-AP at 1/5000, MA5-49175* at 1/500, MA5-50816** at 1/10000 and MA5-54020** at 1/15000. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.